

TRIGGERS

USING DESIGN TO CHANGE HABITS

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ABSTRACT

Triggers was a 16-week classroom investigation into how to use communication design to change habits. Students in this graduate-level class partnered with a classmate, identified habit loops, prototyped and tested possible solutions that could bring awareness to the problem (making design changes as needed), tracked the quantitative and/or qualitative changes, and measured how behavior changed. Topics ranged from procrastination, creative confidence, eating less meat, calling your mom more often, doodling in more productive ways, and grinding your teeth less.

Students focused on a human-centered, holistic, and empathic approach, and applied Design Thinking methodologies to their challenge. Students had an adequate amount of time to understand how design can change behaviors and some outlined their methodology in the form of a toolkit that others might use to change their habits.

KEYWORDS: *habits, behavior change, multi-disciplinary, toolkits, strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Graphic designers work in an ephemeral media. Unlike architects and urban planners who shape public spaces, and product and industrial designers who create useable objects, the passive nature of communication design makes its success inherently more difficult to measure. Nevertheless, graphic designers follow user-centered processes that can help them work across disciplines to find solutions to challenges of various scales. This inspired us to challenge our students to use graphic design in ways that might change a personal habit. We hoped that by focusing on problems at a small, personal scale, we could better-assess the influence that communication design has on people. We were also inspired by the range of recent insights about the nature of how habits form and can be changed.

RESEARCH

First, Wendy Woods and David Neal are two behavioral psychologists who have written about the role that environments play in our habits. According to their research, 45 percent of our daily behavior is repeated. Woods says that we are "integrated" with our environment because we spend most of

our time in just a few locations, whether that be at home, work, school, or in transit, where it becomes easy to form complex routines and a myriad of habits. We used this insight to encourage our students to consider the spaces where they spend most of their time and also referenced *The Power of Habit: Why We Do What We Do in Life and Business*,² a book by journalist Charles Duhigg, in which he examined personal, corporate, and societal habits. Duhigg writes about how many problems start as individual actions that often go on to form habits, which are then reinforced by a myriad of seemingly harmless factors. All of which make up a "habit loop."

Figure 1: The Habit Loop

"Habit Loop" is Duhigg's term and it consists of a cue, a routine, and a reward. Duhigg thoroughly explains these in his book and uses them to illustrate how we might manipulate our habits. Cues are the factors that trigger our habits: particular locations, times, emotional states, other people, or an action that immediately precedes the habit. Routines are the behaviors you want to change. Rewards satisfy the cravings that drive our behaviors.

ASSIGNMENT

This project took place in a class, which involves students applying design-thinking methodologies to social issues. This particular class aimed to transform the behaviors of individuals and communities in desirable ways while creating meaningful experiences and interactions. For this particular project, students were charged with the task of identifying one habit they wanted to stop or start.

We called the project "Triggers."

PROCESS

We often feel challenged by the short amount of time that a 16-week semester allows for projects to evolve. We wanted students to have the whole semester to work on the project in hopes that the extra time would produce more insights and better results overall. So we started the project on the very first class. Students had about 15 minutes to choose one habit that they wanted to either stop or start, then they partnered up with a classmate who they would work with during the whole term. The first couple of weeks were dedicated to defining the problem. Part of this included understanding what we called the "ecosystem" of the habit, or all of the factors that might contribute to it. We led "brainwalking" exercises, which are more dynamic forms of brainstorming and mind-mapping. Students jotted down the habit that they wanted to stop or start on a long sheet of paper and then rotated to each different habit and added what they know about the habit. We expected that a lot of students would focus on health or hygiene-related topics, but were happy to see a broad range of issues: procrastination, eating less meat, creative confidence, doodling in more productive ways, one pair of students focused on calling their mom more often, productivity, and grinding teeth less, for example. On the third week, students came to class with an infographic poster that described their partner's habit and how they planned to use design to help their partner. The impressive range of posters each identified the "habit loops" and their specific opportunities to disrupt the habits (or create new ones in some cases).

During most of the semester, students prototyped potential design solutions that could bring awareness to the problem (making design changes as needed), tracked and measured the quantitative and/or qualitative changes that took place, assessed how well the solutions worked and, in some cases, redefined their project altogether because of what they

Figure 2: Measuring Behavior Change

learned along the way. Students customized their design solutions to meet the unique patterns of their partners' lives. Some students used analog strategies to effectively collect the kind of information that can help them better understand the habit while tracking and measuring their partners' change in behavior, while others used digital technologies like websites and apps.

When we discussed the projects with just a few weeks left in the semester, it was clear that all students changed in some way because of the project. We asked them to tell the story of their project and found that simply building awareness about the habit helped them to change their behavior: by understanding the habit loop, designing objects and systems to address challenges, and regularly tracking the change in their behavior. In fact, by simply summarizing the outcomes of their collaborations, they discovered even more nuances about their habit and projects. Here are five of those twenty projects.

PROJECTS

Putting a Halt on Teeth Grinding

Our first student grinds his teeth sometimes, but he would not consider it a habit, just something that happens if he is more tired than normal, or if he's trying to choke down words that he does not want to come out. He realized that his partner grinds his teeth when he is stressed. So, our first student designed a facial massage technique book to help him distress, as well as a teeth-grinding logbook.

Figure 3: Putting a Halt on Teeth Grinding

Figure 4: Stop Interrupting People

Figure 5: Remember to Call Your Mom

Figure 6: Produce Less Trash

Figure 7: From Meat Lover to Flexitarian

Stop Interrupting People

Our second student has a habit that can sometimes be annoying; she interrupts people during conversations. She was completely oblivious to this, so her partner designed a fun and unique way to warrant her attention, by creating a mobile clicker app that would allow her to log how many times she would do this in a day. She also created a citation packet that her friends could give to her whenever she would interrupt them.

Remember to Call Your Mom

As children we live with and depend on our mothers to teach us how to navigate daily life. Soon enough, however, we grow up and move away; our routine interactions fade. How can we maintain a meaningful relationship with our long-distance moms? For this third project, two students created a diary log that helps you document your conversations with your mom, so that you remember why you should keep calling.

Produce Less Trash

As an action becomes routine, the habit shapes identity. By changing his habit, our fourth student, who developed the routine of producing too much trash, sought to create a new identity. By using social media, his desires and shopping patterns were analyzed and new habits formed.

From Meat Lover to Flexitarian

Eating meat was our fifth student's dilemma. In order to lessen the guilt trip generated by every meal this project aimed to help him transition to a flexitarian regime, moving his meat-heavy diet in a more vegetarian direction. Going meatless on Mondays, photographing his meals, documenting his struggles and triumphs on a blog and providing recipes were all strategies to help him change his habit.

SCALE

While the scale of these one-to-one projects are small, students learned skills that they can apply to greater social challenges. The variety of these small-scaled projects also serve as a mirror for the range of larger, societal issues that could be addressed, one of which students worked on during the same class. This other project involved students looking at the social behavior of different New York City communities affected by Hurricane Sandy. Their challenge was to use design as a means to promote and encourage preparedness and resiliency efforts within these communities and the students applied the same design strategies from the Triggers project to a wider audience, while also looking for ways to track and measure how people were responding to the designs. While more complex design challenges require a larger set of considerations, we learned that the strategic approach of de-

signing to change behavior (which includes finding ways to track and measure a design's impact) can increase the overall effectiveness and impact of design challenges at any scale.

TOOLKITS

The results of these projects prove design's effectiveness to change and improve behaviors, and they encourage us to continue exploring how design can be used to improve even the small facets of our lives. When students told the story of their project at the end of the semester, some wanted to share what they learned with a wider audience. They summarized their findings and approach in toolkits that others can use to stop and start the same habits.

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